

Urolithins in Human Breastmilk after Walnut Intake and Kinetics of *Gordonibacter* Colonization in Newly Born: the Role of Mothers' Urolithin Metabotypes

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1 **ABSTRACT:** The maternal-infant transmission of several urolithins through breastmilk and
2 the gut colonization of infants by urolithin-producing bacterium *Gordonibacter* during their first
3 year of life were explored. Two trials (Proof of concept study: $n = 11$; Validation study: $n = 30$)
4 were conducted where breastfeeding mothers consumed walnuts as a dietary source of
5 urolithin precursors. An analytical method was developed and validated to characterize the
6 urolithin profile in breastmilk. Total urolithins ranged from 8.5 to 176.9 nM while they were not
7 detected in breastmilk of three mothers. The mothers' urolithin-metabotypes governed the
8 urolithin profile in breastmilk, which might have biological significance on infants. A specific
9 qPCR method allowed monitoring the gut colonization of infants by *Gordonibacter* during their
10 first year of life, and neither breastfeeding nor vaginal delivery was essential for this. The pattern
11 of *Gordonibacter* establishment in babies was conditioned by their mother's urolithin-
12 metabotype, probably because of mother-baby close contact.

13

14 **KEYWORDS:** polyphenols, ellagitannins, ellagic acid, Coriobacteriia, Eggerthellaceae, microbial
15 metabolism, urolithin-producing bacteria.

16

17 ▪ INTRODUCTION

18 Walnuts are a substantial source of vitamins, minerals, proteins, unsaturated fats, fiber, and
19 bioactive phenolic compounds such as ellagitannins (ETs) and ellagic acid (EA). ETs and EA
20 present in nuts, pomegranates, berries and oak-aged wine among other food, are metabolized
21 by characteristic colonic bacteria producing specific bioactive metabolites known as urolithins.¹
22 A recent study has shown that walnuts intake modulates gut microbial communities, including
23 an increase of urolithin-producing bacterium *Gordonibacter*.² Although it is speculated that part
24 of urolithins could be further metabolized in the gut, these are absorbed and circulate as
25 glucuronide and sulfate conjugates, and as such, are detected in plasma, urine, and tissues such
26 as the prostate, colon, and mammary gland.³⁻⁵ Urolithins show anti-inflammatory, antioxidant,
27 anticarcinogenic, antimicrobial, cardioprotective and neuroprotective effects *in vitro* and in
28 animal models.^{1,6,7} The evidence in human studies is still limited although the improvement of
29 mitochondrial and cellular health in elderly individuals by urolithin consumption has recently
30 been described.⁸ Differences in health effects observed *in vivo* after consumption of ETs-rich
31 foods could be explained, at least partially, by the large inter-individual variability in the
32 production of urolithins, derived from differences in the gut microbiota composition.⁷ Thus, the
33 beneficial effects are not only a question of production vs. non-production of urolithins but also
34 related to the type of urolithins produced. This variability allows stratifying the population into
35 three groups, called urolithin metabotypes (UMs).⁹ Metabotype A (UM-A) individuals produce
36 only urolithin A (Uro-A; 3,8-dihydroxy-urolithin). Metabotype B (UM-B) is characterized by the
37 production of urolithin B (Uro-B; 3-hydroxy-urolithin) and(or) isourolithin A (IsoUro-A; 3,9-
38 dihydroxy-urolithin) in addition to Uro-A. Finally, individuals from metabotype 0 (UM-0) are
39 those urolithin non-producers. While UM-A and UM-B can change over age, 10% of the
40 population remains constant as UM-0 from 5 to 90 years.¹⁰ UMs are associated with differences
41 in the gut microbiota profile.¹¹⁻¹³ Furthermore, the genus *Gordonibacter* can produce urolithins
42 and has been positively correlated with UM-A and Uro-A production in humans versus either

43 UM-0 or UM-B.^{9, 14–16} Uro-A, recently reported as a Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS), is the
44 predominant metabolite detected in the plasma and urine of urolithin producers (UM-A and
45 UM-B). Several health benefits have been attributed to Uro-A, primarily intestinal anti-
46 inflammatory properties, while Uro-B and IsoUro-A, although less studied, are also bioactive
47 metabolites with similar effects than Uro-A.⁷

48 The acquisition and colonization of the microbiome in the first weeks of life play a crucial
49 role in the development of the immune system, and set the stage for the adult microbiome.^{17,18}
50 This process is shaped by many factors including infant feeding (breastfed or formula-fed), type
51 of delivery (vaginal or caesarean section), gestational age at birth, maternal lifestyle,
52 geographical location, intake of antibiotics and other medications, and host genetics.^{17,19}
53 Although 90% of children aged between 5 and 10 years old can produce urolithins, according to
54 a study with a Caucasian cohort (5–90 years, n = 839),¹⁰ it is unknown when and how gut
55 colonization by urolithin-producing bacteria, such as *Gordonibacter*, occurs in infancy.
56 Breastfeeding is one of the most significant factors associated with gut microbiome
57 establishment during the first year of life.²⁰

58 The determination of dietary phenolics in breastmilk, their metabolizing bacteria and the
59 metabolites produced, has still been little explored. There are only a few studies, and most of
60 them focused on isoflavones^{21–25} and other flavonoid metabolites.^{26–30} Little is known about the
61 existence of urolithins or urolithin producing bacteria in breastmilk. Only the presence of
62 glucuronide conjugates of Uro-A and Uro-B have been reported in human breastmilk^{31,32} from
63 only two and one volunteers, respectively. Unlike other biological samples (urine, feces, blood,
64 etc.) for which different methodologies have been validated,³³ an optimal and validated method
65 for determining these compounds in breastmilk matrix has not been established so far. Besides,
66 essential aspects such as the influence of the mother's UM on the urolithin composition of
67 breastmilk or the *Gordonibacter* colonization in infants have not been considered.

68 Therefore, this work aimed to: i) evaluate urolithin production in breastmilk after walnut
69 intake and whether mothers' UMs determine the urolithin profile, and ii) explore possible
70 relationships between maternal UMs, and type of feeding (breastfed or formula-fed) and
71 delivery (vaginal or caesarean) with the colonization of the urolithin-producing bacteria
72 *Gordonibacter* in infants.

73

74 ■ MATERIAL AND METHODS

75 **Chemical and Reagents.** Urolithin A 3-glucuronide (Uro-A 3-glur; 8-hydroxy-urolithin 3-
76 glucuronide), isourolithin A 3-glucuronide (IsoUro-A 3-glur; 9-hydroxy-urolithin-3-glucuronide),
77 urolithin B glucuronide (Uro-B glur; urolithin-3-glucuronide), urolithin A sulfate (Uro-A sulfate;
78 8-hydroxy-urolithin-3-sulfate), urolithin B sulfate (Uro-B sulfate; urolithin-3-sulfate), urolithin
79 M6 (Uro-M6; 3,8,9,10-tetrahydroxy-urolithin), urolithin M7 (Uro-M7; 3,8,10-trihydroxy-
80 urolithin), isourolithin A (IsoUro-A; 3,9-dihydroxy-urolithin), urolithin A (Uro-A; 3,8-dihydroxy
81 urolithin), and urolithin B (Uro-B; 3-hydroxy-urolithin) were chemically synthesized and purified
82 by Villapharma Research S.L. (Parque Tecnológico de Fuente Álamo, Murcia, Spain). Urolithin D
83 (Uro-D; 3,4,8,9-tetrahydroxy-urolithin) and urolithin C (Uro-C; 3,8,9-trihydroxy-urolithin) were
84 purchased from Dalton Pharma Services (Toronto, Canada). Stock solutions (10 mM) of
85 individual urolithins were prepared in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and standards mixtures were
86 prepared in methanol at a concentration of 200 μM. Standard of EA and the internal standards,
87 6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (DHC), and chrysin were from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Their
88 stock solutions were prepared in methanol. All standard solutions were stored at -20 °C.

89

90 Methanol and acetonitrile were purchased from J.T.Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands).
91 Formic acid and acetic acid were from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Milli-Q system

92 (MilliporeCorp., Bedford, MA, USA) ultrapure water was used throughout this experiment. All
93 chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

94 Packs of peeled walnuts were kindly provided by Borges International Group, S.L. (Reus,
95 Tarragona, Spain). Peeled walnuts were subjected to acid hydrolysis and analyzed by HPLC-DAD-
96 MS/MS³⁴ to quantify free EA (4.1 ± 0.6 mg/g fresh weight) as the primary precursor of urolithins.

97 **Study Design and Participants.** Two trials (Trial 1: Proof of concept study; Trial 2: Validation
98 study) were carried out according to the Helsinki Declaration and its amendments. Ethics
99 committees from the Servicio Valenciano de Salud (reference 52327) (Valencia, Spain) and the
100 Spanish National Research Council (CSIC, Spain) (reference AGL2015-64124-R) authorized the
101 protocols. In both trials, the exclusion criteria were: consumption of medication, antibiotics, or
102 dietary supplementation such as probiotics or prebiotics one month before and during the
103 study. Ellagitannins-containing foods (pomegranate, walnuts, strawberries, etc.) were avoided
104 during the week before starting the intervention with walnuts. All the participants were
105 informed and gave written, informed consent for study participation.

106 *Trial 1* was a pilot study to determine the time required to detect urolithins in breastmilk
107 after starting walnut intake and to develop a method for urolithins extraction in human
108 breastmilk samples. Healthy women ($n = 11$) after delivering a healthy newborn and with
109 breastfeeding were recruited at different postpartum stages (between 2 weeks and 24 months
110 after giving birth) because breastmilk composition generally differs over time. Ten mothers
111 consumed 30 g of peeled walnuts daily for three days as previously described for urolithin
112 detection in urine.⁸ They kindly provided breastmilk at 0 h, 24 h, 48 h, and 72 h and urine samples
113 at 72 h from starting walnuts intake, respectively. One of the mothers did not consume the
114 walnuts for 3 days, and her breastmilk sample was used as a blank for the validation studies.

115 *Trial 2* was a more extensive study to characterize the urolithin profile in breastmilk
116 depending on the UMs of the donors and evaluate the colonization of *Gordonibacter* in infants
117 during the first year after birth. For this purpose, healthy women ($n = 30$) were selected from a

118 cohort of 40 mothers whose gut microbiota and anthropometric profiles during the first year
119 postpartum were previously described.³⁵ In this *Trial 2*, three weeks after delivering a healthy
120 baby by vaginal (70%) or caesarean (30%) delivery, the mothers consumed 30 g of peeled
121 walnuts daily for 3 days, and they kindly provided breastmilk and urine samples at 72 h from
122 starting walnuts intake. Finally, only 27 volunteers could provide breastmilk samples. Mothers
123 ($n = 30$) also provided stool samples from their babies four times during their first year of life (1,
124 4, 6 and 12 months) to study when and how the baby's intestine is colonized by *Gordonibacter*
125 and the relation with the mother's UM.

126 **Sample Collection.** Infant feces and breastmilk samples were collected following a
127 standardized protocol provided. Women self-collected both samples at home. Infant feces were
128 collected in sterile containers directly from the diaper. Breastmilk samples were collected in
129 parallel. In brief, the protocol included a breast cleaning step with water and soap. Then,
130 breastmilk was collected from one breast by use of a sterile pumper in sterile bottles to
131 normalize the breastmilk collection protocol. Morning collection was recommendable. Feces
132 and breastmilk samples were aliquoted and stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further analysis.

133 **Determination of Urolithin Metabotypes of the Mothers.** Urine samples at 72 h from
134 starting walnuts intake were used to stratify the mothers of both trials by UMs, analyzing the
135 production of urolithins and their phase II metabolites. Samples were vortexed for 30 sec,
136 centrifuged at $14,000 \times g$ for 10 min, and filtered through a $0.22\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ polyvinylidene fluoride
137 (PVDF) filter (Millipore, Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain). Samples were diluted 1:2 with water
138 containing 0.1% formic acid. The analyses were carried out using an Agilent 1200 HPLC (Agilent
139 Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with a photodiode array detector and a single
140 quadrupole (single Q) mass spectrometer detector (HPLC-DAD-ESI-Q (MS)), following the
141 protocol described elsewhere.³³

142 **Breastmilk Sample Preparation for Urolithins Extraction.** Two different strategies for milk
143 sample pre-treatment and extraction of original urolithins were evaluated: protein precipitation

144 with various reagents, and separation using solid-phase extraction. Blank samples spiked with
145 0.5 μ M of a mixture of urolithins were subjected to different extraction protocols.

146 Acetonitrile (ACN), methanol (MeOH), and a pre-treatment with *n*-hexane were tested to
147 remove proteins and lipids. ACN and MeOH were acidified with formic acid (0.5, 1, and 2%) or
148 hydrochloric acid (1.5%) to enhance the separation of phases after centrifugation. Besides,
149 different solvents [MeOH, MeOH/ACN (50/50, v/v) and ACN] were also assayed to re-dissolve
150 the samples after the evaporation of the supernatant.

151 Regarding solid-phase extraction, 1 mL of clarified milk (previously centrifuged) was diluted
152 with water acidified with different percentages of formic acid, and filtered through a C18 Sep-
153 Pack cartridge. After washing with 5 mL of water, compounds were eluted with 2 mL of MeOH.
154 We also tested hybridSPE-phospholipid technology (Sigma-Aldrich, San Luis, MO, USA) for
155 removing phospholipids and proteins from the milk matrix. The final protocol optimized for
156 urolithins extraction is further detailed in the Results Section.

157 **UPLC-ESI-QTOF MS Analysis.** Samples were analyzed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity UPLC
158 system coupled to a 6550 Accurate-Mass Quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) (Agilent
159 Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). The chromatographic and mass spectrometric conditions
160 tested were those previously optimized for the quantification of urolithins in other biological
161 samples (urine, plasma, and feces).³³ Briefly, the separation was achieved on a reversed-phase
162 Poroshell 120 EC-C18 column using as mobile phases: water plus 0.1% formic acid (phase A) and
163 ACN plus 0.1% formic acid (phase B) in a gradient mode. The flow rate was 0.5 mL/min, and the
164 injection volume was 5 μ L. Spectra were acquired in negative polarity with *m/z* range 100-1100.
165 Data were processed using the MassHunter Qualitative Analysis software (version B.10, Agilent
166 Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany).

167 *Method Validation.* The method was validated in terms of linearity, sensitivity,
168 repeatability, matrix effects, and recovery based on the validation guidance of analytical
169 methods.³⁶

170 *Calibration curves* of all available urolithins were prepared in MeOH and the milk matrix
171 from 0.001 μ M to 5 μ M. For the latter, blank samples, taken for a volunteer from *Trial 1* not
172 consuming ellagitannin-rich products, were extracted as described in the result section and
173 spiked after the extraction with the mixture of urolithins at different concentrations (post-spike
174 samples) to take into account possible matrix effect. An internal standard (dihydroxycoumarin
175 (DHC)) was added in each sample before sample preparation in order to control extraction
176 efficiency.

177 *Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ)* were calculated using the most diluted
178 standard solutions prepared in the milk matrix, considering a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of 3 for
179 the LOD and of 10 for the LOQ (IUPAC method).³⁷

180 *Repeatability* was evaluated by injecting three concentrations of the urolithin mixture
181 prepared in the matrix, three times on the same day (intra-day repeatability) and different days
182 (inter-day repeatability).

183 *Matrix effect (%ME)* for each urolithin was calculated comparing the slopes of calibration
184 curves in MeOH and in matrix (post-spiked sample): %ME= ((slope matrix-slope MeOH)/slope
185 MeOH)*100. If the ratio is within \pm 15%, no matrix effect was considered.³³

186 *Recovery* was evaluated by spiking blank samples with urolithins at three concentration
187 levels: 0.01, 0.1, and 0.5 μ M, each in triplicate. After vortexing, the samples were extracted as
188 described in the result section. Recovery was calculated by comparing the peak area of target
189 compounds in the samples spiked before the extraction with those spiked after the extraction.

190 **Determination of *Gordonibacter* in Breastmilk and Infant Stool Samples.** Bacterial
191 genomic DNA was extracted from 2 mL-breastmilk samples as described before,³⁸ and from
192 infant stool samples following the manufacturer's instructions of the NucleoSpin[®] Tissue DNA
193 Purification Kit (Macherey-Nagel, Dueren, Germany). NanoDrop ND-2000 (NanoDrop
194 Technologies, Wilmington, DE, USA) was used to determine DNA concentration. In breastmilk
195 and stool samples, a touch-down real-time qPCR was carried out for *Gordonibacter* DNA

196 amplification as described elsewhere¹⁴ with an ABI 7500 Real-Time PCR system. Samples were
197 analyzed in triplicate and compared with a standard curve of genomic DNA (6-fold serial
198 dilutions of *Gordonibacter pamelaee* DSM 19378^T).

199 **Statistical Analysis.** Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS Software, version 23.0
200 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The kinetics of urolithin excretion in breastmilk over 72 h of walnut
201 consumption was evaluated by repeated measures analyses of variance (ANOVA) followed by
202 Bonferroni-corrected *t*-test (for post-hoc analysis) (*Trial 1*). Mothers were grouped into UMs
203 while babies, depending on the analysis, into their mothers' UMs, feeding mode, type of
204 delivery, or presence/absence of *Gordonibacter* in the feces (*Trial 2*). A multinomial logit model
205 was applied to evaluate differences in *Gordonibacter* gut colonization in babies over the first
206 year after childbirth (1, 4, 6, and 12 months), according to mothers' UMs or type of delivery.
207 Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

208

209 ■ RESULTS

210 **Optimization of a Method for Urolithins Extraction in Human Breastmilk Samples.** ACN
211 showed a better effect on protein precipitation compared to MeOH, which yielded lower
212 efficiency (from 30-60%, depending on the metabolite). The acidification improved the
213 precipitation of proteins, but hydrochloric acid hampered the recovery of the conjugates
214 (glucuronides and sulfates) by promoting their hydrolysis to the corresponding free forms. Best
215 recoveries and fewer matrix effects was observed with 1% of formic acid. A previous wash with
216 *n*-hexane decreased the recovery of some urolithins, especially those unconjugated metabolites.
217 Regarding solid-phase extraction, sample acidification seemed to affect the recovery of the
218 compounds, and hydrolysis of the conjugates, especially sulfates, was observed when using high
219 percentages of formic acid. In general, good recoveries for most metabolites were obtained with
220 less interference from the co-eluted endogenous matrixes, although with poorly reproducible

221 results. When hybridSPE-phospholipid technology was used, recoveries for most free forms
222 were high ($\geq 85\%$). However, the most polar compounds, such as the conjugates and some poly-
223 hydroxylated free forms (Uro-D, Uro-M6, and Uro-C), showed recoveries below 40%.

224 Finally, in the optimized method, breastmilk samples (1 mL) were mixed with 3 mL of
225 ACN:formic acid (99:1, v/v), and 20 μL of internal standard (2 ppm 6,7-dihydroxycoumarin) was
226 added. Samples were vortexed for 1 min, incubated under agitation in an ultrasonic bath for 10
227 min, and centrifuged twice at 18,000 $\times g$ for 30 min at 4 °C. The resulting supernatant was dried
228 in a speed vacuum concentrator (Savant SPD121P, ThermoScientific, Madrid, Spain). The
229 evaporated samples were dissolved in 200 μL of methanol and filtered through a 0.22 μm PVDF
230 filter. A second internal standard (0.1 ppm chrysin) was added just before the analysis by UPLC-
231 ESI-QTOF. This method was rapid, simple, and allowed a good recovery by minimizing the
232 possibility to lose analytes during the sample clean-up process.

233 **Method Validation.** The parameters of the validation method are shown in **Table 1**.
234 Recovery values ranged between 62 and 76% for glucuronide and sulfate conjugates of Uro-A
235 and Uro-B, respectively, whereas recovery values for free forms were higher, between 66% for
236 Uro-M7 and 92% for Uro-B. Acceptable recoveries were obtained for all the compounds
237 considering the complexity of the matrix (**Table 1**). All calibrations curves showed good linearity
238 ($r^2 \geq 0.995$) in a wide range of concentrations from LOQ to 5 μM . The LOD was very low for
239 glucuronide conjugates (6.0 nM for Uro-A glur, 5.8 nM for IsoUro-A glur, and 4.2 nM for Uro-B
240 glur) and a bit higher for sulfate conjugates (7.3 nM for Uro-A sulfate and 10.3 nM for Uro-B
241 sulfate). Lower LOD values were found for the unconjugated forms, 1.5 nM for Uro-A, 1 nM for
242 IsoUro A, and 5 nM for Uro-B. LODs and LOQs in breastmilk for these urolithins were in the same
243 range that those found in urine. Results of intra- and inter-day repeatability showed values of
244 relative standard deviation (RSD) for the peak area ratios below 4.8% for intra-day and below
245 8.6% for inter-day repeatability, showing a good level of precision. The values of matrix effects
246 were within a tolerance range of $\pm 15\%$, and indicated that there were no matrix effects for these

247 compounds.^{39,40} The matrix effect was higher than -15% for other analytes, reflecting moderate
248 suppression of the signal. In any case, to reduce the matrix effect, a matrix-matched standard
249 curve was used for quantification.

250 **The kinetics of Urolithins Excretion in Breastmilk.** Breastmilk samples from volunteers of
251 the pilot study (*Trial 1*) were used to identify the presence of urolithins over time as donors were
252 in different lactation stages and to evaluate their excretion kinetics in breastmilk over 72 h.
253 Chemical structure and extracted Ion Chromatograms (EICs) of the main urolithins detected in
254 human breastmilk are represented in **Figures 1** and **2**, respectively. Walnut intake led to the
255 excretion of glucuronide and sulfate conjugates of Uro-A, IsoUro-A, and Uro-B [Uro-A glur (**1**),
256 IsoUro-A glur (**2**), Uro-A sulfate (**3**), Uro-B glur (**4**) and Uro-B sulfate (**5**)]. Besides, peaks of the
257 unconjugated forms IsoUro-A (**6**), Uro-A (**7**), and Uro-B (**8**) were also detected (**Figure 2**).
258 Urolithins were found in urine samples from all mothers who consumed walnuts in *Trial 1* ($n =$
259 10). In contrast, in three of them ($n = 1$ from UM-A and 18-month-old baby; $n = 2$ from UM-B
260 and 2- and 5-month-old babies, respectively), urolithins were not detected in breastmilk at any
261 time, because they were not present or were below the LOD. In the rest of the volunteers ($n =$
262 7), Uro-A glur was the predominant metabolite in breastmilk, whereas other urolithins were
263 detected in only a limited number of samples. Although urolithin concentrations were always in
264 the nanomolar range (data not shown), high inter-individual variability was observed in the
265 urolithins profile in milk. Volunteers, with detectable urolithins in breastmilk during walnut
266 intake, were grouped into UM-A ($n = 4$) and UM-B ($n = 3$) (**Figure 3**). The kinetics of urolithins
267 excretion showed a progressive increase of urolithins in breastmilk over time ($P < 0.001$). The
268 maximum value was reached at the last sampling point (24 h after the last walnut intake) with
269 no significant difference between UMs (UM-A mean value = 28.3 ± 12.1 nM and UM-B mean
270 value = 28.8 ± 14.6). For this reason, breastmilk sampling for urolithins determination in *Trial 2*
271 (which included more volunteers than *Trial 1*) was selected at 72 h.

272 **Quantification of Urolithins in the Breastmilk of Mothers with Different UMs.** The UMs of
273 the mothers in *Trial 2* ($n = 30$) were determined by analyzing their urine samples 72 h after
274 walnut intake started. From the 27 mothers who finally provided breastmilk samples, 12 were
275 UM-A (44%) and 15 UM-B (55%). As occurred in the preliminary study (*Trial 1*), none of the
276 mothers belonged to the UM-0. The urolithin concentrations in both UMs, and each mother
277 individually, are shown in **Tables 2** and **3**, respectively. There were no significant differences in
278 urolithin concentration between breastmilk samples from *Trial 1* (established lactation: > from
279 1 month) and *Trial 2* (early lactation: 3 weeks).

280 Breastmilk samples of UM-A mothers were characterized by the presence of glucuronide
281 and sulfate conjugates of Uro-A. In contrast, breastmilk samples of UM-B mothers contained
282 conjugates of IsoUro-A and(or) Uro-B in addition to those of Uro-A (**Tables 2** and **3**). Among
283 urolithins, Uro-A glur, a common compound in both UM-A and UM-B, was the predominant
284 metabolite (it was detected in 26 out of the 27 volunteers, with a detection rate of 92%) with an
285 average concentration of 27.6 nM for UM-A and 31.1 nM for UM-B (**Tables 2** and **3**). No
286 significant differences were observed in the amount excreted of Uro-A-glur between both UMs.
287 Uro-A sulfate was only detected in four volunteers (33%) within UM-A, and quantified in two of
288 them (average concentrations 7.9 nM). In contrast, a larger occurrence was observed in mothers
289 with UM-B (80%) with higher levels (17.2 nM). Some mothers with UM-B also excreted IsoUro-
290 A glur and(or) Uro-B glur (53 and 67% of the mothers, respectively), but the concentration of
291 most of these concentrations were below the LOQ (6.2 and 3.7 nM, respectively). The average
292 levels were 14.8 nM for IsoUro-A glur and 19.8 nM for Uro-B glur. Uro-B sulfate was only
293 detected in 2 mothers with UM-B, but the concentrations were below the LOQ (10.1 nM).
294 Regarding unconjugated urolithins, their concentration in breastmilk was very low (≤ 5 nM). Uro-
295 A was detected in both UM-A and UM-B (detection rate of 42 and 33%, respectively), and
296 average concentrations of 4.7 and 3.3 nM for UM-A and UM-B, respectively. Six mothers with

297 UM-B (40%) excreted IsoUro-A (average concentration of 2.7 nM), and only one excreted Uro-B
298 in milk (4.3 nM) (**Tables 2 and 3**).

299 **Infant Gut Colonization by the Urolithin-Producing Bacteria *Gordonibacter*.** Most of the
300 newly born (n=29) who completed the one-year study (n = 30) consumed breastmilk during the
301 first month of their life. A gradual and significant reduction ($P < 0.001$) in breastfeeding from 1
302 to 12 months after giving birth was observed. Thus, most of the 12-month-old babies (82%) were
303 no longer breastfed. The presence of *Gordonibacter* in infant fecal samples was analyzed during
304 first year of life (1, 4, 6, and 12 months). The concentration of *Gordonibacter* in infants ranged
305 from below the detection limit (<2 log copies/g) to 8.4 log copies/g feces with a mean value of
306 4.4 ± 2.3 log copies/g. *Gordonibacter* was already detected in 45% of the 1-month-old babies.
307 Interestingly, *Gordonibacter* was also detected in the fecal samples of the only baby who never
308 was breastfed, even when he was 1-month-old. No associations between feeding type and
309 presence of *Gordonibacter* in babies were found in the first year of life (results not shown).
310 Furthermore, *Gordonibacter* was below the limit of detection (<2 log copies/mL) in breastmilk
311 samples.

312 Infants were clustered depending on their mother's UM, and the presence of *Gordonibacter*
313 in fecal samples was analyzed (**Figures 4A, 4B**). In babies born from UM-A mothers,
314 *Gordonibacter* was detected in 47% of one-month-old babies. The presence of *Gordonibacter*
315 significantly increased ($P = 0.025$) until 78% in four-month-old babies, and it was maintained
316 without significant changes until the end of the study (12 months from birth) (**Figure 4A**). In
317 contrast, in babies born from UM-B mothers, the presence of *Gordonibacter* was detected in
318 53% of one-month-old babies, and the increase in *Gordonibacter* incidence was not produced
319 until 12-month-old babies, being later than in babies born from UM-A mothers (**Figure 4B**). Once
320 the presence of *Gordonibacter* was detected in the babies, its abundance was significantly
321 unchanged over time in most of the babies regardless of their mothers' UMs.

322 Infant clustering according to the type of delivery revealed that 46% and 40% of one-
323 month-old babies born by vaginal or caesarean delivery, respectively, presented *Gordonibacter*
324 in their feces (**Figures 4C, 4D**). The colonization kinetics by *Gordonibacter* was nearly identical in
325 both types of delivery. At the last stage, 84% and 86% of twelve-month-old babies born by
326 vaginal or caesarean delivery, respectively, presented *Gordonibacter* in their feces. Therefore,
327 the type of delivery did not affect the increase of *Gordonibacter* prevalence in babies during
328 their first year of life.

329

330 ■ DISCUSSION

331 Breastfeeding contributes to the protection of the health of the newly born because breastmilk
332 contains nutrients, vitamins, minerals, hormones, antibodies, immune cells, and beneficial
333 bacteria such as bifidobacteria as well as bioactive metabolites (postbiotics) produced by
334 maternal gut microbiota after consumption of some foods.^{26,41,42} Walnuts are a very rich source
335 of ellagitannins and therefore an excellent precursor for urolithin production. Previous studies
336 have shown that the intake of 30 g walnuts for three days provides enough ellagitannins to
337 enable the characterization of urolithin metabotypes in humans.^{2,43,44} Walnuts are a more
338 optimum source of human urolithin precursors compared to other EA containing foods such as
339 pomegranate. Indeed, a previous study showed that the walnut-matrix rich in fat favors the
340 availability of EA-related compounds to urolithin production by the human gut microbiota
341 compared to pomegranate.⁴⁵ During breastfeeding, urolithins could confer additional anti-
342 inflammatory activity to human breastmilk, but their identification in this matrix has been poorly
343 explored. The complexity of the milk matrix explains why the determination of polyphenol-
344 derived metabolites such as urolithins in breastmilk has been hardly investigated and why an
345 optimal and validated method has not been developed until now. It is essential to remove milk
346 protein and fat content before analysis as previously suggested.³⁰ Most previous studies have

347 determined polyphenols in human milk after enzymatic hydrolysis and subsequent extraction
348 with ethyl acetate or diethyl ether.^{21-23,25,27,29} Protein precipitation with ACN has also been used
349 in previous works to quantify total phenolic compounds in breastmilk using the Folin-Ciocalteu
350 method³⁰ and isoflavones after enzymatic hydrolysis.²⁴ However, in these cases, relevant
351 information about the naturally occurring metabolites is missing. In other work, solid-phase
352 extraction was applied to determine phase II metabolites of epicatechin.²⁶ In the present study,
353 ACN was selected versus MeOH because of the better recoveries. Similarly, ACN was also used
354 to extract isoflavones from human breastmilk.²⁴ Centrifugation was selected to improve the
355 precipitation of protein and lipids as previously described.^{24,27,30} A more extended extraction
356 protocol combining protein precipitation with ACN followed by solid-phase extraction on C18
357 cartridges was used to extract Uro-A glur in human breastmilk samples after pomegranate juice
358 consumption.³² No information about recoveries and validation parameters was provided to
359 compare those results with our study. For the first time in the present study, a method to
360 quantify urolithins in breastmilk has been fully optimized and applied in two trials. LOD and LOQ
361 differed between the different urolithins. The main reason is that compounds with similar
362 structure can have different response in the mass spectrometer. Good sensitivity was obtained
363 with this methodology, showing LOD for Uro-A glur in breastmilk (1.8 nmol/L) in the same range
364 and even lower as that shown previously (4.95 nmol/L).³²

365 In *Trial 1*, the excretion kinetics of total urolithins in the breastmilk of 10 mothers was
366 evaluated during 72 h after starting walnut intake as previously optimized for urolithin detection
367 in urine.⁴⁴ Maximum urolithin concentrations in breastmilk was found on day 4 (72 h after the
368 start of walnuts intake). This accumulation over time, even on day 4 where mothers did not
369 consume walnuts, is due to the fact that urolithins remain in circulation for 12 to 72 h after
370 consumption.^{1,46} Enterohepatic circulation is responsible for the long clearance of these
371 metabolites, which persist in urine for 48-72 h after ellagitannin-containing food intake.
372 Subsequent intervals were not analyzed because mothers did not continue consuming walnuts

373 beyond three days. The qualitative urolithin profile of human milk was similar to that previously
374 found in plasma and urine, with glucuronide and sulfate conjugates as the predominant
375 compounds, and the free forms present at much lower concentrations.^{9,33} Therefore, urolithins
376 can be excreted in breastmilk regardless of their chemical structure. Blood metabolites,
377 including those derived from the metabolism of dietary (poly)phenols by the gut microbiota, are
378 excreted into breastmilk by passive and active processes, as described for enterolignans in
379 different animals where the participation of the ABCG2 transporter is critical.^{47,48} In the case of
380 urolithins, their absence in some human breastmilk samples could be due to the large inter-
381 individual variability in urolithins production, i.e., high vs. low urolithin producers, which could
382 prevent the occurrence of detectable urolithins in the milk in those urolithin low-producers.³ In
383 the present study, the levels of Uro-A glur detected in breastmilk (from 8.7 to 90.9 nM) were in
384 the same order of those detected in plasma (around 110 nM) after the intake of walnuts.³
385 Regarding breastmilk, these values are also in the order of those found in the breastmilk of two
386 mothers after the intake of pomegranate juice (from 21.5 to 36.3 nM).³² However, these
387 coincident values are somewhat unexpected, taking into account that Uro-A glur levels were
388 estimated by MS using Uro-A as standard, which has a very different signal-response from Uro-
389 A glur in MS.³³ Nanomolar urolithin concentrations in breastmilk were also in agreement with
390 the breastmilk ranges of other polyphenols previously reported. In a recent study, the
391 phytoestrogens genistein, daidzein, equol, and enterolactone were detected with total average
392 concentrations of 270 nM.²⁵ Franke et al. also reported daidzein and genistein levels in human
393 breastmilk at 80-110 and 30-50 nmol/L, respectively, after the consumption of soy-rich diets.^{21,23}
394 The presence of different flavan-3-ols (epicatechin, epicatechin gallate, gallic acid gallate)
395 and other flavonoids (naringenin, kaempferol, hesperetin, and quercetin) in human milk samples
396 was also reported at nanomolar levels.^{26,28,29} Although all these values are in the nanomolar
397 range, differences in the concentration of the different polyphenol metabolites in breastmilk

398 may be the result of several factors, including dietary exposure, the efficiency of absorption and
399 transfer from plasma to human milk, among others.²⁹

400 In *Trial 2*, the contribution of UMs of 27 mothers in the composition of their breastmilk was
401 considered. Thus, the type of urolithins excreted in the breastmilk depended on the maternal
402 UMs and were consistent with those found in urine. For the first time, we describe that the
403 urolithin profile in breastmilk was governed by the maternal UMs. Therefore, as in the case of
404 plasma and urine, the urolithins profile in breastmilk indirectly reflects the maternal gut
405 microbiota composition because UMs have been associated with different gut microbiota
406 profiles.¹¹

407 In the present study, the distribution of mothers' UMs was 44% UM-A and 56% UM-B, as
408 previously described in the postpartum period.³⁵ This distribution differs from that reported for
409 a healthy population,¹⁰ and closer to that reported for overweight-obese subjects with mild to
410 high cardiometabolic risk.^{43,49} Uro-A glur was the predominant metabolite present in most
411 breastmilk samples (detection rate 96%) in both UMs. In contrast, IsoUro-A glur and Uro-B glur
412 were only detected in volunteers with UM-B with 53 and 67% detection rate, respectively. These
413 differences in the type of urolithins to which infants are exposed via breastmilk could produce
414 differences in the benefits of breastfeeding associated with urolithins since different health
415 benefits have been attributed to each urolithin type.⁷ Besides, the prebiotic effect of Uro-A has
416 also been previously described in a colitis rat model.⁵⁰ Therefore, the consumption of urolithins
417 through breastfeeding could also contribute to the gut microbiota modulation of infants.
418 However, further research about the direct and indirect health effects of urolithins in breastfed
419 infants, especially against infant colic, should be explored.

420 Comparison of both trials did not show significant differences in urolithin concentration
421 between breastmilk of *Trial 1* (established lactation samples: more than 1 month from delivery;
422 $n = 7$) and *Trial 2* (early lactation samples: 3 weeks from delivery; $n = 27$). According to the
423 lactation stage, a previous study also showed no difference in the concentration of metabolites

424 from other polyphenols (flavonoids) in breastmilk. In contrast, other non-polyphenolic
425 compounds such as carotenoids decreased significantly from weeks 1 to 13 of lactation.²⁹ In the
426 present study, most breastmilk samples were obtained 3 weeks from delivery and only 7 from
427 later stages of lactation. Therefore, further research should be done to confirm that urolithin
428 content is stable during different stages of lactation.

429 Gut colonization in infancy by the urolithin-producing bacteria *Gordonibacter* has not been
430 previously explored. This genus is essential for the production of bioactive urolithins, which can
431 not be produced by 10% of the population of any age.¹⁰ It is known that the richness and diversity
432 of the fecal microbiome of newly born are lower than that of adults. Besides, 16S rRNA Illumina
433 sequencing is less sensitive than real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR). Therefore, only a specific
434 qPCR method¹⁴ allowed us to detect and quantify *Gordonibacter* in infant feces for the first time.
435 Indeed, *Gordonibacter* was present in 45% of 1-month-old babies. It is known that the type of
436 feeding (breastfed or formula-fed) and delivery (vaginal or caesarean section) are two of the
437 most important factors, among others, involved in establishing the gut microbiota in neonatal
438 and infant periods.^{17,19} However, our results show that neither breastfeeding nor vaginal delivery
439 was an essential condition for the colonization of *Gordonibacter*. Thus, *Gordonibacter* was
440 detected in fecal samples from some 1-month-old babies delivered by caesarean section and
441 the only baby that was not ever breastfed. This agrees with a previous study, which showed that
442 within the first 6 weeks of life, the infant microbiota undergoes substantial reorganization,
443 primarily driven by body site and not by type of delivery.⁵¹

444 It is still unknown the precise beginning of the colonization of *Gordonibacter* since our
445 follow-up started four weeks after delivery. This colonization increased in babies from one to
446 twelve months, regardless of the type of delivery. Interestingly, *Gordonibacter* occurrence
447 sharply increased up to 78% in 4-months-old babies from UM-A mothers despite their sources
448 of bacterial colonization are scarce because at that age they still do not crawl. In contrast, in
449 breastfed infant from UM-B mothers, the colonization was delayed for 6 months, and

450 *Gordonibacter* occurrence only increased from 6 to 12 months after birth. Furthermore, the
451 relative abundance (%) of *Gordonibacter* in the gut was significantly higher in UM-A mothers
452 than UM-B during the first year postpartum, as previously reported.³⁵ Therefore, close contact
453 of mothers with their babies during their four months of life may favor colonization probability
454 with *Gordonibacter*, especially in babies born from UM-A mothers.

455 In the present study, a method has been optimized and successfully applied to characterize
456 the metabolic profiling of urolithins in breastmilk by LC-MS, and to explore, by using qPCR, the
457 colonization of the newly born by *Gordonibacter*. Overall, this combined method allowed the
458 identification of 8 different urolithin metabolites in breastmilk after walnut intake and described
459 the colonization kinetics by *Gordonibacter* in the first year of the babies' life. Although urolithins
460 are excreted into breastmilk at nanomolar concentrations, they could contribute to
461 breastfeeding's anti-inflammatory properties and healthy properties. Besides, it was confirmed
462 that breastmilk resembles the UMs of the mothers, which might have biological significance for
463 the infants. Therefore, our study opens new research scenarios to explore the role of walnuts
464 and breastfeeding with urolithin-enriched milk on infants' health and microbiota modulation.
465 *Gordonibacter* colonization in infants occurs through their first year of life, and neither
466 breastfeeding nor vaginal delivery was an essential condition for this. However, the kinetics of
467 *Gordonibacter* colonization in babies is conditioned by their mother's UM.

468

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481 **Notes**

482 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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693

694 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

695 **Figure 1.** Urolithin metabolites detected in human breastmilk after the intake of walnuts.
696 **(1)** 8-Hydroxy-urolithin-3-glucuronide (urolithin A-glucuronide); **(2)** 9-Hydroxy-urolithin-3-
697 glucuronide (isourolithin A-glucuronide); **(3)** 8-Hydroxy-urolithin-3-sulfate (urolithin A-sulfate);
698 **(4)** Urolithin 3-glucuronide (urolithin B-glucuronide); **(5)** Urolithin 3-sulfate (urolithin B-sulfate);
699 **(6)** 3,9-Dihydroxy-urolithin (isourolithin A); **(7)** 3,8-Dihydroxy-urolithin (urolithin A); **(8)** 3-
700 Hydroxy-urolithin (urolithin B).

701

702 **Figure 2.** Extracted Ion Chromatograms (EICs) of the main urolithins detected in human
703 breastmilk after the intake of walnuts. 1) Uro-A glur; 2) IsoUro-A glur; 3) Uro-A sulfate; 4) Uro-B
704 glur; 5) Uro-B sulfate; 6) IsoUro-A; 7) Uro-A; 8) Uro-B.

705

706 **Figure 3.** Excretion kinetics of total urolithins in breastmilk of UM-A and UM-B mothers
707 from *Trial 1* during walnut consumption. Statistical significance was evaluated by repeated
708 measures analyses of variance (ANOVA) followed by post-hoc Bonferroni-corrected *t*-test. **The*
709 *three volunteers without detectable urolithins in breastmilk were not included.*

710

711 **Figure 4.** (A) Presence of *Gordonibacter* in fecal samples from babies born from UM-A
712 mothers, or (B) born to UM-B mothers, by (C) vaginal delivery, or (D) caesarean delivery.

713

714

Table 1. Validation parameters for the quantification of urolithins in human breastmilk.

	Recovery (%)	LOD (nM) a/b	LOQ (nM) a/b	Precision (RSD%)		ME (%)
				(intra-day)	(inter-day)	
Uro-A 3-glur	67 ± 2	6.0/1.8	20.0/6.0	2.0	2.6	-6.3
IsoUro-A 3-glur	62 ± 1	5.8/1.9	19.2/6.2	4.8	3.7	-20.2
Uro-A sulfate	76 ± 1	7.3/1.9	24.3/6.4	2.6	8.1	-18.1
Uro-B glur	76 ± 8	4.2/1.1	14.1/3.7	4.5	7.3	+5.7
Uro-B sulfate	68 ± 4	10.3/3.0	34.5/10.1	2.0	4.3	-25.1
IsoUro-A	72 ± 3	1.0/0.3	3.4/0.9	4.1	6.0	-36.8
Uro-A	76 ± 6	1.5/0.4	5.0/1.3	3.5	4.5	-29.0
Uro-B	92 ± 3	5.0/1.1	16.7/3.6	2.5	8.6	-8.5
Uro-C	84 ± 7	0.8/0.2	2.8/0.7	4.0	2.6	-16.9
Uro-M7	66 ± 4	12.0/3.6	39.7/12.0	0.2	4.3	-29.8
Uro-D	79 ± 9	1.3/0.3	4.4/1.1	1.5	7.4	-18.5
Uro-M6	76 ± 9	1.4/0.4	4.6/1.2	0.7	8.3	-23.2

LOD: Limit of detection; LOQ: Limit of quantification; a) LOD and LOQ of the instrument, calculated in the sample injected; b) LOD and LOQ in the original sample, before extraction and injection; ME: Matrix effect; RSD: Relative Standard Deviation.

Table 2. Mean concentration (nM) of urolithins in breastmilk of mothers ($n = 27$, *Trial 2*) grouped by urolithin metabotypes (UMs).

Urolithins	UM-A mothers ($n = 12$)		UM-B mothers ($n = 15$)	
	Mean \pm SD; (range)	Samples ^a	Mean \pm SD; (range)	Samples ^a
Uro-A glur	27.6 \pm 22.9; (8.7 – 77.9)	10/11	31.1 \pm 24.8; (9.5 – 90.9)	12/15
Uro-A sulfate	7.9 \pm 1.8; (6.6 – 9.2)	2/4	17.2 \pm 11.8; (6.5 – 40.4)	11/12
IsoUro-A glur	<LOD	0	14.8 \pm 8.6; (6.3 – 23.4)	3/8
Uro-B glur	<LOD	0	19.8 \pm 21.6; (4.5 – 51.7)	4/10
Uro-B sulfate	<LOD	0	<LOQ	0/2
Uro-A	4.7 \pm 1.0; (3.9 – 5.4)	2/5	3.3 \pm 2.6; (1.4 – 7.8)	5/5
IsoUro-A	<LOD	0	2.7 \pm 1.4; (1.7 – 5.1)	6/6
Uro-B	<LOD	0	4.3	1/1

^a Samples represent the number of volunteers where each metabolite was quantified/detected; <LOQ (Limit of quantification): metabolites are detectable but the exact amount cannot be quantified; <LOD (Limit of detection): metabolites are not detectable.

Table 3. Concentration (nM) of urolithins in breastmilk of mothers ($n = 27$, *Trial 2*) grouped by urolithin metabolotypes (UMs).

Volunteer	UMs	Uro-A glur	Uro-A sulfate	IsoUro-A glur	Uro-B glur	Uro-B sulfate	Uro-A	IsoUro-A	Uro-B
M2N1	UM-A	14.4	Det.	-	-	-	-	-	-
M4N1	UM-A	77.9	9.2	-	-	-	5.4	-	-
M6N1	UM-A	20.0	Traces	-	-	-	-	-	-
M7N1	UM-A	8.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M10N1	UM-A	13.5	Traces	-	-	-	Det.	-	-
M20N1	UM-A	14.7	Traces	-	-	-	-	-	-
M26N1	UM-A	23.5	Det.	-	-	-	Det.	-	-
M35N1	UM-A	Det.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M38N1	UM-A	23.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M39N1	UM-A	61.0	6.6	-	-	-	3.9	-	-
M40N1	UM-A	19.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M50N1	UM-A	-	-	-	-	-	Det.	-	-
M1N1	UM-B	23.3	8.6	-	-	-	2.6	-	-
M9N1	UM-B	9.5	6.7	Det.	Det.	-	Traces	1.8	-
M11N1	UM-B	9.9	Det.	Det.	-	-	-	-	-
M14N1	UM-B	Det.	-	-	Det.	-	-	-	-
M15N1	UM-B	24.7	36.8	14.8	Det.	-	-	5.1	-
M18N1	UM-B	90.9	14.5	-	51.7	7.7	7.8	-	4.3
M22N1	UM-B	34.7	19.9	Det.	Det.	-	1.6	1.7	-
M23N1	UM-B	11.7	19.3	6.3	13.3	Traces	-	2.5	-
M25N1	UM-B	Det.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M28N1	UM-B	31.5	6.5	-	9.9	Traces	1.4	-	-
M32N1	UM-B	17.7	20.0	Det.	-	-	-	1.7	-
M33N1	UM-B	15.3	7.3	Det.	Det.	5.9	-	-	-
M42N1	UM-B	37.5	9.4	-	4.5	-	3.3	-	-
M43N1	UM-B	Det.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M44N1	UM-B	67.1	40.4	23.4	Det.	-	-	3.3	-

*Det., Detected but not quantified (below LOQ). Traces means that these metabolites are detected close to the limit of detection (LOD).

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

TOC GRAPHIC

